

Religion and Ethnicity in Nigeria: Challenges to National Development

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Abstract

As a multi-ethnic, multi-religious country, Nigeria is a pluralistic society with a conglomeration of more than 250 ethnic nationalities with different cultural and religious orientations with African Traditional Religion, Christianity and Islam as its three main religions. The ethnic and religious composition of Nigeria and its manipulation by the political elites has posed a lot of challenges to development, governance and security in Nigeria. Diligent assessment of the rate of development in any given society calls for a proper examination of the roles of religion in the lives and conducts of the people. Religion binds, restores hope, builds and develop a nation, where religion is practiced with a sincere worship to God, it is the strongest tool for development. On the contrary, religion in Nigeria functions as a means for the perpetration of violence, fueling ethnic consciousness and solidarity, acquisition of political power and socio-economic gains, massive killings and the wanton destruction of lives and properties which results to under development and setbacks. This paper takes a cursory look at how Religion and Ethnicity have challenged the development of the Nigerian state and recommends among others the need to address leadership recruitment system. And religious leaders in Nigeria should teach their adherents that religion is one's personal relationship with God and Nigerians should learn to be more tolerant and accommodative to one another irrespective of our ethno-religious differences to pave way for peace, good governance and development. Documentary method of data collection and qualitative descriptive analysis is employed to put the paper together.

Keywords: Religion, Ethnicity, Pluralism, Challenge, National Development

Introduction

Politics in Nigeria over time has mingled with ethnic, cultural and religious influences in such a way that it has become impossible to identify clearly the sources of conflicts that is ravaging and negating all efforts to develop Nigeria. The unfortunate tale about Nigeria is that both ethnic and political hostilities are given religious names. Notwithstanding the various efforts of the government to checkmate these problems such as adoption of the federal system of government, multiple state creation, federal character and quota system, national youth service corps scheme, unity schools, multiple party system, campaigns for free and credible elections, religious and secular peace talks etc. the country ever than before is still divided along ethnicity and religion. This paper takes a cursory look at how Religion and Ethnicity have challenged the development of the Nigerian state and recommends among others the need to address leadership recruitment system. And religious leaders in Nigeria should teach their adherents that religion is one's personal relationship with God and Nigerians should learn to be more tolerant and accommodative to one another irrespective of our ethno-religious differences to pave way for peace, good governance and development. Documentary method of data collection and qualitative descriptive analysis is employed to put the paper together.

Ethno Religious Composition of Nigeria

As a multi-ethnic, multi-religious country, Nigeria is a pluralistic society with African Traditional Religion, Christianity and Islam as its three main religions.¹ Nigerians are deeply religious and are acknowledged by British Broadcasting Cooperation² as the most religious nation in the world. It has been argued that Nigeria has become the number one country globally in terms of the population of religious worshippers and adherents,

notably, of the two major religions, Christianity and Islam.³ Nigeria is among the most religious countries in the world. According to the Pew Research Centre, Nigeria is at the top of the chart in terms of intense religiosity. Both Christianity and Islam have experienced very dramatic growth over the last 50 years. They have not just experienced quantitative growth, but they have experienced very important qualitative changes – changes in denominational affiliation, changes in theology, and changes in attitude towards one another.⁴

Nigeria's broad religious demography reflects the historical exposure of its northern communities to Islam through the Trans-Saharan Trade and the success of Christian Missionary Enterprise in many of its southern parts. However, while historical alliances and shared ethnicities are closely associated with the adoption of these two world religions, religion and ethno-regional identities are cross-cutting, often reinforcing each other. Beyond the engagement with local traditions, Christianity and Islam as major religions in Nigeria have expressed a high degree of political competitiveness with each other at least, since the 1970s.⁵ Apart from Christianity and Islam, Nigerians also belong to a range of other religious groups. The largest of these comprise followers of traditional religious practice, known as African Traditional Religion (ATR) with the provision that local belief systems and practices differ widely, and that their subsumption under one term mainly reflects the fact that these practices do not (yet) hold the status of world religions.⁶

Within the two major religions in Nigeria (Islam and Christianity), there has been internal divisions and subdivisions that sometimes produce sharp contentions. Islam and Christianity are rivals to each other. Apart from being rivals to each other, they (Islam and Christianity) are suppressing the traditional religion. Religion which is supposed to be the agent of peace, unity and harmony is a sharp contrast in Nigeria and elsewhere. Nigeria has recorded series of religious crises, claiming lives and property which are hindrances to national development. The issue of religion in Nigeria is becoming more complex with apparent hostilities, frictions and crises. Indeed, religion is threatening the corporate existence of the nation as well as undermining the political integrity of the country. Religious crises in Nigeria are major obstacles to peace and development in the country.

Hank asserts that, just as football is singularly the sole and most unifying factor in Nigeria, nothing is as divisive as religion—especially when it is used as a tool of politics.⁷ Nigerian politicians have used religion to divide the country just as they have used ethnicity to fan the embers of our national dichotomy. In Nigeria, religion has become a tool of politics and not as a belief system. Evidently, we are no longer able to maintain the fundamental principles of a secular state like religious freedom and governments patronizing particular religions. The sanction and enforcement of Sharia Laws in the criminal court by some state governments have also compounded the problem.

According to B. Anuforo, recent developments and memories of past and continuous carnage in Northern Nigeria on the innocent and for reasons beyond comprehension are beginning to sway the position of many, who previously frowned at the thought of alternative system of co-existing.⁸ In other words, while believing and hoping on a united, progressive, secular and God-fearing country, staunch Nigerian nationalists are now open to the possibility of a different form of mutually agreed arrangement. For example, the break-up of Nigeria to accommodate the conflicting regional, religious and tribal aspirations of ethnic groups. The Governor-General of Nigeria between 1920-1931, Sir Hugh Clifford, described Nigeria as, “A collection of independent native states, separated from one another by great distances, differences of history and traditions and by ethnological, racial, tribal, political, social and religious barriers.”⁹ The above description seems to vividly capture the problems of today's Nigeria, where too many innocent lives have been sacrificed because of religion.

Nigeria is not only a plural society with several ethnic and religious groups, but one where ethnic and religious boundaries overlap. The ethno-regional-cum-religious overlaps add troubling twists and turns to the configuration. The need to curtail the threat this poses for nation-building informs the constitutional adoption of secularism in Nigeria. Nigerian constitutions, past and present, proclaim loudly the secularity of the Nigerian state, the separation of church, and state and the freedom to practice religion of one's choice without fear of persecution and prosecution.¹⁰ Section 1, Sub-Sections (1) and (2) of the 1999 Nigerian constitution provide that:

This constitution is supreme and its provisions shall have binding force on all authorities and persons throughout the Federal Republic of Nigeria. The Federal Republic of Nigeria shall not be governed, nor shall any person or group of persons take control of the government of Nigeria or any part thereof, except in accordance with the provisions of this constitution.¹¹

Section 10 of the constitution categorically proclaims that, “The government of the Federation or of a State shall not adopt any religion as state religion.” Section 38 of the 1999 constitution under fundamental rights stresses the freedom of worship in the following words: “Every person shall be entitled to freedom of thought, conscience and religion, including freedom to change his religion or belief, and freedom (either alone or in community with others, and in public or in private) to manifest and propagate his religion or belief in worship, teaching, practice and observance.”

Drawing from the above, the constitution bars a state from adoption of a religion, and any attempt by anyone to foist a religion on the nation by a political fiat or, indeed, any form of deceit. However, the Nigerian constitution recognizes only Islam as a religion, no any other faith is mentioned in the Nigerian constitution, except Islam. Sharia is mentioned 73 times, Grand Khadi 54 times, Islam 28 times and Muslims 10 times. The constitution also recognizes the need and application of the Sharia Law—but only to those whose religion is Islam. Section 260 of the Nigerian constitution gives room for the establishment of the Sharia Court of Appeal of the Federal Capital Territory Abuja. “There shall be a Sharia Court of Appeal of the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.” Officially, Nigeria is a secular state with freedom of religion guaranteed in the 1999 constitution. Through secularism, Nigeria seeks not only to maintain some form of neutrality and independence on religious matters, but allows Nigerians religious freedom. The essence is to draw a boundary between the two realms—state and religion and by so doing, reduce the negative influence of religion on nation building.

Nigeria is a pluralistic and multi-diversified society, in terms of her composition and culture, Nigeria is the third most ethnically and linguistically diverse country in the world, after New Guinea and Indonesia,¹² Nigeria is a nation with a population of over 218,325,756 as of November 22, 2022 based on world meter elaboration of the latest united nations data Nigeria is made up of several ethnic groups majority of which are the Igbo, Hausa and the Yorubas. Within these ethnic groups are several tribes numbering 371. A great variety of environment within the Nigerian territory, ranging from dense rain to swamp forest to open semi-arid grassland, has encouraged a wide measure of cultural differentiation and ethnic-cum religious fragmentation.

The issue of ethnic identity underlies Nigeria experience like nothing else since her inception as a country. Ethnicity and religion have eaten deep into the very fiber of our nation like Achebe pointed that “nothing in Nigeria’s political history captures her problem of national integration more graphically than the checkered fortune of the word ‘tribe’ in her vocabulary.”¹³ Be it politics, economy, education, religion, social relation etc., ethnic prejudice is conspicuously manifested in Nigeria, ethnic origin and religion in a fundamental element in determining and delimiting what her citizen gets in employment, political appointment, university admission, distribution of social amenities, election and even marriage, the interest is narrowed down to ethnicity and religion.

The quest for ethnic relevance through the control of political power always triggered off cries of marginalization among the ethnic groups in the imbalance in the distributions of the national fiscal resources. Every ethnic group in Nigeria cries oof marginalization and the multiple effects include unhealthy ethnic competitions, hatred, insecurity, accusation and counter accusation, ethno-religious conflicts, political instability, land dispute, indigen and non-indigen palaver and the emergence of ethnic militias who seek for either a fair share of the national cake or outright balkanization of Nigeria. “The politics of marginalization ... has encouraged violence and insurgence as the only means through which one can get the ear of the federal government.”¹⁴ Inequalities in power, economy, status, properties and prestige perpetuated by prejudice are the basis of most socio-political conflicts in Nigeria. Ethnicity, according to D. Bell, “has become a means for disadvantaged groups to claim a set of rights and privileges which the existing powers have denied them.”¹⁵

Ethno-Religious Riots in Nigeria

Nigeria was amalgamated in 1914, only about a decade after the defeat of the Sokoto Caliphate and other Islamic states by the British which were to constitute much of present-day Northern Nigeria. After the first World War, Germany lost the colony of Cameroon to France, Belgian and British mandates. Cameroon was then divided into French and British parts. The latter of which was further subdivided into southern and northern parts. Following a plebiscite in 1961, the Southern Cameroon opted to join Nigeria, a move which added to Nigeria's already large Northern population. The territory comprised much of what is now North-Eastern Nigeria, and a large part of the area affected by waves of insurgencies in recent history.

K. Suleiman also noted that, another serious area of colonial state policy which has exacerbated Christian-Muslim tensions and sown the seed of suspicion is the way the colonial state dealt with relations between the Muslim North and those non-Muslim communities which the colonial state contemptuously referred to as the animist communities in the Middle Belt.¹⁶ The same region that is presently under constant attack by Fulani herdsmen and religious fanatics killing citizens and destroying properties. After conquering the Sokoto Caliphate in 1903, the colonial state strangely turned around to establish an enterprise of collaboration with the vestiges of the feudal establishment. In doing this, the colonial state created both an umbrella of protection for the Muslim communities and walls of suspicion between the communities in many major cities in Northern Nigeria.

Despite the above background to sow the seed of religious conflicts in Nigeria by the British administration, there were no major religious crises during the colonial era; most of what one might call religious crises was really conflicts between various factions within the Muslim communities in the Northern region. For example, the internal conflict between the dominant brotherhoods, namely, the *Khadiryya* and the *Tijaniyya* and the so-called *Mahdist* revolts, otherwise known as *Mahdism* in colonial historiography, raged on against the colonial state from the Sudan to many parts of Northern Nigeria.¹⁷ Another area of crisis between the colonial state and the Muslim community, according to Suleiman, arose from the issue of the status and scope of Islamic (Sharia) law within the colonial state.¹⁸

In spite of the above earlier trend, the first major religious conflict in Nigeria was in 1953, in Tafawa Balewa in present day Bauchi State. The Igbo massacre of 1966 in the North that followed the counter-coup of the same year had caused the Igbo officers' coup and pre-existing (sectarian) tensions between Igbo and the local Muslims.¹⁹ The 1980s saw an upsurge in religious violence beginning with *Maitatsine* up to the present-day Boko Haram terrorist organization that is linked to Islamic State in Syria (ISIS). Nigeria has experienced a succession of ethno-religious and socio-political crises that have resulted in the loss of thousands of lives, and property worth billions of Naira. The number of lives and amount of money and value of property lost in Nigeria every year as a result of religious crises and riots are beyond the scope of this study.

Over the years, there has been a plethora of literature from eminent Nigerian scholars on the issue of religious violence. F. Duniya, observes that "religious riots have a recurring decimal in the nation leading some important Nigerians to raise their voices against this ugly trend. It has created a great chasm in the unity of the nation in general,"²⁰ Nigeria has experienced a succession of ethno-religious and socio-political crises that have resulted in the loss of thousands of lives and property worth billions of naira. E. E. Anugwom *et al* captured the above reality in the following words, "Throughout recorded history in West Africa and indeed black Africa in general, Nigeria seems to rank top among the list of nation-states that have witnessed the most perturbing and unprecedented upsurge of ethnic and religious disturbances in contemporary times ... it has remained a constant threat to peace in Nigeria."²¹

The Fulani herdsmen and farmers' crisis that cuts across Nigeria but has been more intense in the Middle Belt with a large population of Christian farmers is one of the issues that have been given a religious interpretation. Thousands have been killed and many more homes, places of worship and foodstuffs have been destroyed. There have always been crises between Fulani herdsmen and farmers across the country before now, but the rate at which they commit these crimes has increased exponentially. The herdsmen have unabatedly continued to wreak havoc, mostly in the Middle Belt/North-Central area of Nigeria that is predominated by Christians and farmers.

The Fulani herdsmen, nomadic cattle grazers have been named one of the deadliest terror groups in the world comparable to Boko Haram, ISIS, the Taliban and al-Shabab. They brutally kill natives of invaded farming communities including women and children. Church leaders in Nigeria have come up to say that, attacks on Christian communities by the herdsmen constitute a war by Islam to eliminate Christianity in Nigeria. The Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN) while declaring 8 January, 2017 as a National Day of Mourning over Southern Kaduna killings by Fulani herdsmen lamented that:

Though the Church in Nigeria since 2009 has been subjected to a systematic genocide and persecution through the instrumentality of Islamic fundamentalists, Boko Haram, leading to the killing of thousands of Christians and destruction of hundreds of churches, and over 50,000 houses, but the current unprecedented onslaught against Christians in Southern Kaduna by the Islamic fundamentalists disguising as the Fulani herdsmen under the watch of Kaduna State Government, Mallam Nasir El-Rufai and President Muhammadu Buhari has reached an alarming stage.²²

In a press conference by the Catholic Diocese of Kafanchan in reaction to killings in Southern Kaduna, the Diocese in its statement pointed to the fact that Southern Kaduna had become victims of systematic attacks by the Fulani herdsmen who were hell bent on pursuing an agenda that was aimed at subjugating the Southern Kaduna people and weakening the Gospel. The Diocese alleged that, it was a hidden agenda targeted at the Christian majority of Southern Kaduna and the Jihad was well funded, well planned and executed. The above records clearly show that Central Nigeria accounts for the largest portion of religious crises in Nigeria. J. H. Mamman and P. B. Tanko recorded that, between 1980 and 2004, there had been more than 150 incidents of conflict in Kaduna State alone, in which more than 2000 people lost their lives, over 50,000 people were injured and 4000 people displaced.²³ Plateau State is not left out. In fact, it is doubtful if Jos as a state capital can ever be itself again owing to the amount of destruction resulting from religious crisis. As stated earlier, various reasons have been advanced for the animosity between Christians and Muslims in Nigeria; the reasons are not far from socioeconomic disparities, lack of equal access to political positions, denial of rights and privileges, assumption of superiority of one religion over the other, discrimination in employment and so on.

It is now on record according to the United States (US) House of Representatives that Nigeria is the most dangerous place for Christians to live in the world. The US Congress condemned the attacks on Nigerian Christians and also said that the impunity of people responsible for killing Christians in Nigeria is in proliferation. According to a *ThisDay* report by Adebowale, the Chairman of its subcommittee on Africa, Global Health, Human Rights and International Organization, Christopher Smith, made the above statement in a letter inviting former President Goodluck Jonathan to make a presentation to the subcommittee on the challenges faced by Christians in Nigeria and the Niger Delta issue.²⁴ Smith in the letter made exclusively available to *This Day* (2017) said that,

My sub-committee has broadly investigated the crisis facing Christians in Nigeria today. My staff Director, Greg Simpkins and I have made several visits to Nigeria, speaking with Christians and Muslim religious leaders across the country and visiting fire-bombed churches, such as in Jos. Unfortunately, Nigeria has been cited as the most dangerous place for Christians in the world and impunity for those responsible for the killing of Christians seem to be widespread. In fulfilment of your foundation's mandate to promote democracy, peace and transformational change, I invite you to come to the United States next week to share your views on this matter, including the alleged Islamization of government under the current administration and the actions your foundation is prepared to take in pursuit of religious freedom.²⁵

Jonathan was invited by the subcommittee in his capacity as Chairman of the Goodluck Jonathan Foundation. In his address to the subcommittee, Jonathan called for the implementation of the resolutions of the 2014 National Conference as a panacea for ethnic and religious tensions in Nigeria. He identified impunity as a factor contributing to the recurrence of violence, such as the one in Southern Kaduna, noting that if those behind previous crises were not prosecuted; other individuals and groups would be emboldened to repeat the same acts. On the

issue of the Niger Delta crises, Jonathan said he fully aligned with the views of the 2014 National Conference, which called for true and fiscal federalism as the way out of agitations in the region and in other parts of Nigeria.

A cursory look at the records of religious violence in Nigeria, according to Salisu, brings out clearly some trends. Firstly, and most importantly, it may appear that the crises are caused mainly by religious reasons. However, in reality, the reasons go beyond religion to include political and economic factors. P. T. Williams in his own opinion argued that, as the political class in Nigeria lacks national acceptance and cannot spearhead a national mobilizing ideology, it increasingly resorts to the politicization of ethnicity, fetishization of religious differences, and the awakening of pristine and atavistic norms and practices.²⁶ Nigeria as a nation has experienced a succession of religious crises that have resulted in the loss of thousands of lives and property worth billions of naira. Nwabuzo in Isiramen envisaged that:

The nation called Nigeria is slipping gradually into extinction. Factually, we have no nation, just a geographical expression. Nigeria is currently a country where no lives and property are safe; a country where government is a collection of selfish individuals; a country where so-called gentleman's agreement is not binding and honour becomes a game. The result of this is cataclysm.²⁷

Although Nigeria is one of the richest countries in the world, constant religious crises have contributed in increasing poverty, hatred, acrimony, lack of patriotism, to mention but a few. Speaking on the effect of religious violence in Nigeria, V. Onwukene maintains that:

The side effect of violence leaves numerous women widows and countless number of children fatherless and motherless. It often leaves so many homeless and jobless. Property worth billions of naira has been lost through religious violence. Apart from many who die in it, some people are left mutilated and handicapped for life. Thus, these conflicts bring with them, terrible consequences like loss of human lives and property, traumatic experiences, anger, hostility, animosity, resentment and hurt that are sores and these can be difficult to heal for years.²⁸

Politicization of Ethnicity and Religion in Nigeria

Religion and politics have caused many countries to either grow or separate. In Nigeria, every government is judged by the way power is distributed. Anything contrary to attaining a religious balance status triggers a wide cry of marginalization. The struggle for power in Nigeria predated independence, but it was based on ethnic, economic and social factors. It was in the event of the 1966 coup that religious meaning and antagonism began to be associated with political activities.²⁹ Some scholars argued that the Igbo as a tribe was the major target because not all Christians in the North were affected.

In many Third World Countries, religion is embedded in their politics and cultures, and its impact on politics is correspondingly more pronounced than the Western World. The extent at which religions influence political attitudes and behaviour and the degree of political involvement by organized religions vary considerable from one country to another. The effect of religion on politics also varies from one country to another, while in some countries, religious involvement in politics chart the course for a better cohesion and development. In other countries, religion creates division and social disintegration.³⁰

In Nigeria, the relationship between religion and politics has been given various interpretations. There are opposing views on the role of religion in Nigeria's politics. Some critics consider organized religions as an obstacle to the achievement of political development, while others insist that religious belief can motivate believers to work for the unity and progress of the country. The relationship between religion and politics continues to be an important theme in Nigeria's polity, despite the emergent consensus on the right to freedom of conscience and on the need for some sort of separation between religion and the Nigerian State. Religion plays an important role in the lives of Nigerians and as such, there is a link between politics and religion in Nigeria.³¹

D. F. Asaju suggested politicization of religion in the body polity of the state. He relied heavily on the opinion of Theophilus Danjuma, who suggested that, "Religious fanaticism and favouritism have also been

politically employed to polarize the people and sustain unhealthy tension in Nigeria.”³² This situation points directly to the fact that religion has negatively affected politics. However, it should be noted that politics has equally affected religious thoughts, practices and beliefs in the country. The three dominant religions in Nigeria are Traditional Religion, Islam and Christianity. The ideologies of these religions allow for interaction between religion and politics.³³

In Nigeria, it is hard to separate religion from politics. Religious leaders in Nigeria do work hand in hand with their political allies to create more problems for the country instead of concentrating on their responsibilities in the process of nation building. Some contributions to the debate on the role of religion towards nation building have argued that the prevailing conscious deviation from the principles of religious leaders might soon lead to the extinction of religion in Nigeria as an agent for propelling social change. Even among religious leaders themselves, concerns have been expressed that the replacement of love, truth, oneness and unity, which had been the roots on which all faith had been based, with such vices as self-centeredness, lies and falsehood, greed and hatred bred by fanaticism, has eroded the respect that was once accorded to religion and its leaders.³⁴

Religion, politics and ethnicity have always been used in Nigeria during electioneering campaigns, but in 2003, it was very glaring that religion was used openly as a tool for political gains. The campaign for the 2003 elections was particularly characterized by calls for separation and for recognizing of the potential danger of religion. The All-Nigerian Peoples’ Party (ANPP) presidential candidate, Muhammad Buhari, in 2003 was alleged to have said that Muslims should vote only for a Muslim president. “As the year 2003 elections drew closer, former Head of State, General Muhammadu Buhari (Rtd.) called Muslims across the country to vote only for a presidential candidate that would defend and uphold the tenets of Islam.”³⁵

The controversy as to whether he really said that raged on throughout his campaigns in the 2003, 2007, 2011 and 2015 presidential elections and has never been settled even now that he has won the presidential election under the All Progressives Congress (APC). Below is the relevant section of his speech translated from Hausa by Musa Umar Kazaure and quoted by Boer thus:

Make sure you do not listen to a person who will use his position or money to influence you to vote those who will not support your stand on religion. So, ensure that you vote only those who will fight your cause. A Sokoto man must not be president. A Borno man must not be president. A Kano man must not be president. If the Muslims are united here and in South-West states where Muslims are in the majority, I am sure we can get a Muslim or good Muslims that will rule this country. That is the best thing for us. You must vote somebody who will protect your religion and dignity. If you allow exploiters of religion and your dignity to install a president and continue ruling this country, then, know that they will turn us into their labourers and there is nothing we can do about it. This is the greatest challenge before us and I urge you to enlighten all Muslims on this where ever they are in Nigeria.³⁶

Ajani called the above statement of Buhari, “The albatross of Sharia and religion which still hangs on the head of Buhari till date. The statement is one of the political manipulations of religion, a secular use of religion and abuse of religion, all of which goes against the gains of religion itself. Going by the above statement accredited to Buhari, one is compelled to conclude that the merger between Action Congress of Nigeria (ACN), a party headed by Asiwaju Bola Tinubu, a Yoruba Muslim from the South-West and Congress for Progressive Change (CPC), a party headed by Muhammadu Buhari also a Muslim from the North, to form the All Progressives Congress (APC), that won the 2015 presidential elections goes to confirm the dream of Buhari to have a Muslim president with the merger between the Muslims in the North and South-West. No wonder, the People’s Democratic Party (PDP) terms the All-Progressives Congress (APC) an “Islamic Party.” The PDP’s spokesman, Olisa Metuh, enthusiastically accused the APC of propagating *Janjaweed* ideology. The basis of this accusation was that, the APC at its formative period had a preponderance of Muslims in leadership positions.³⁷

After the APC’s first convention, a new hierarchy emerged reflecting a better religious and ethnic balance. Notwithstanding, suspicions that had been sown in the minds of the impressionable were reinforced with talk that

the party was seriously considering selecting a Muslim-Muslim ticket to challenge President Goodluck Jonathan; a move that both the party (APC) members and others like Obasanjo rejected. According to Agbese, Abdullah and Alkassim of *Daily Trust*, when Asiwaju Bola Ahmed Tinubu, a powerful party leader insisted that he should be nominated as the running mate to Buhari, he was unanimously adopted by the party's South-West Caucus to which the position was zoned, but his nomination was stiffly resisted by party leaders from zones who said, such a Muslim-Muslim ticket would cause untold political problems to the party and the country.³⁸

Similarly, former President Olusegun Obasanjo too differed with Buhari and others on the same religion ticket. Buhari insisted that Nigerians genuinely needed a president and a vice-president who would place Nigeria first and pull it out of the brinks, regardless of whether or not both are Muslims or Christians. Buhari insisted that his position did not make him a fundamentalist as claimed by other people who said that Buhari once professed a love for Sharia so much that he would have loved it to apply throughout the country.³⁹

Obasanjo's position differed from that of Buhari when he noted that a Muslim-Muslim or Christian-Christian presidential ticket at that time of the nation's precarious unity was not only absurd but also out of tune with the present Nigeria. Obasanjo in reacting to Buhari's position said that; "It will be insensitive to the point of absurdity for any leader or any party to be trying with a Muslim-Muslim or Christian-Christian ticket at this juncture. This time is different from any other time". Obasanjo said that, "sensitivity is a necessary ingredient for the enhancement of peace, security and stability at this point in the political discourse and arrangement for Nigeria and for encouraging confidence and trait."⁴⁰ Buhari while defending himself as not a fundamentalist, pointed out that, in 2003, he chose late Chuba Okadigbo as a running mate. He was a Roman Catholic. In 2007, he chose Edwin Ume-Ezeoke. He was also a Roman Catholic. In 2010, he chose Pastor Tunde Bakare. Buhari insisted on having an open mind to picking a Christian or Muslim. In his words, he stressed that: "I firmly believe that Nigerians, having gone through what they have gone through, realize it is not a matter of religion but a matter of Nigeria."⁴¹

With the emergence of Ahmed Bola Tinubu as the flag bearer of the ruling All Progressive Congress (APC) and Senator Kashim Shettima as his running mate only confirm the initial position of Buhari and APC in 2015 to have a Muslim-Muslim ticket with the merger between the Muslims in the North and Muslims in the South-West. The Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN) and other solitary voices have condemned the ticket and called on Nigerian Christians not to vote for APC in the forthcoming 2023 elections. Similarly, former vice president Atiku Abubakar, the presidential candidate of the opposition Peoples Democratic Party (PDP), despite the fact that he picked Delta State Governor Ifeanyi Okowa, a Christian as his running mate thereby fulfilling the unwritten power sharing convention that if the president is a Muslim, the vice president should be a Christian and vice versa. Atiku is still rejected on the basis of ethnicity and zoning, a Fulani Muslim cannot rule for eight years and handover to another Fulani Muslim from the same North which is insensitive to adherence to the power rotation between Muslim dominated north and south dominated Christian.

When it is pointed out that the Muslim-Muslim ticket of chief MKO Abiola and Ambassador Babagana Kingibe of the Social Democratic Party (SDP) roundly defeated the Muslim-Christian ticket of Bashir Tofa and Sylvester Ugoh of the National Republican Convention (NRC) on June 12, 1993 presidential election regrettably annulled, one ready response is that Nigeria is a far more different country today with higher levels of religious intolerance. Ethnoreligious intolerance, extremism and violence is higher now than 1993 because of the worsening material poverty and inequality manifesting particularly in soaring unemployment, pervasive hunger and rising despair and hopelessness among vast majority of Nigerians.⁴²

The present Nigerian state, according to Dekera, is suffering from scores of self-afflicted divisive factors, many of which form the embers of disunity and discord, as well as others which promote mediocrity in all corners of her national life. The factors include ethnic and religious dichotomy, state policies like quota system, federal character and catchment area are detrimental to the growth of the country. The insistence that religion must play a part in the selection of who leads the nation at the federal and state levels appears retrogressive, especially when

such consideration played no prominent role in the leadership selection in the past without any harmful effects to the unity and cohesion of the country, whether under military or civilian governments.

While tracing the politicization of religion during post-colonial Nigeria, Enwerem recalled the disturbing socio-political situation that greeted independence in 1960 and paved the way for the politicization of religion. Firstly, Nigeria found itself in the capitalist world economy, which simultaneously generated a corresponding cadre of Muslims as well as Christians. Also, Nigeria was divided under the domination of two major religions—Islam and Christianity—each in constant struggle for power with each other. Thirdly, the well-educated southerners dominated the civil service and the economic arm of the state while the selected class of Western-educated Islamized Northern elites dominated the political arm of the state. The above reasons set the stage for the kind of politics discernible in post-colonial Nigeria. The issue of religion took a political dimension that has impacted on the country from independence up to the present day. Since independence, Nigeria has struggled unsuccessfully to clearly articulate the relationship between religion and politics. Religion in Nigeria is often instrumentalized for political ends, thereby creating strong animosity among religious groups. The consequences of the dysfunctional configuration of politics and religion is the persistence of religiously induced conflicts in the country in post-colonial Nigeria.⁴³

Conclusion

It is still an irony that Nigeria claims to be one of the most religious nations in the world and yet Nigeria is also one of the most notorious and corrupt nations. Nigeria citizens are insulted all over the world. Even many nations that do not claim to be religious have warned their citizens against doing business with Nigeria. Yet Nigeria has the largest number of Christians in the black world and sends the largest contingents of Muslim pilgrims to Mecca every year. Nation building to religion are at present confused multi-faceted concepts. Although Christians helped to bring western education to Nigeria, the two main religions i.e., Christianity and Islam are not playing any frontline role in the development of the entity called Nigeria.

The two major religions in Nigeria—Christianity and Islam have not done much in combating corruption, disunity, political riots, electoral frauds, ethnic rivalry and discrimination. One's state of origin and tribe in Nigeria determines the type of job one gets, admission into universities, enlistment in Army, Police, Airforce and navy. In terms of national unity, there is need to re-evaluate the place of religion and ethnicity in the Nigeria nation. Religion and ethnicity have divided the country more than bringing unity that is expected. The continuing manipulation and transformation of religious identities for political ends is detrimental to the peace and development of the country. Political leaders should seek to secularize their policies and show neutrality at all times in religious affairs. The Nigerian state for some time now has become an active participant in religious affairs and incapacitated itself in maintaining fairness and equity in its relation with religions, thereby causing secular marginalization and exclusion.

The backbone of ethnicity in Nigeria will be weakened when our leaders will be willing to convene a sovereign national conference where Nigerians will collectively decide on the issue of “oneness” and consequently come up with a constitution on how they want to be governed. The quest for national integration must begin with social and political consensus which recognizes the multi-cultural character of the society and the people's acceptance of co-existence, mutual tolerance and interdependence as a sine qua non for peace and development. It is only through collective willingness to accommodate, tolerate and develop a sense of respect, flexibility, inclusion and relatedness that we can produce the true spirit of oneness and unity in a multi-diversified polity like Nigeria.

The decision of the federal government to remove religion and ethnicity from the nations census is a welcome idea, and need to be enforced by extending it to the removal of “federal character” in the constitution, to encourage hard work, competency, excellence and promote patriotism which is a trend to all civilized plural and secular societies. After all, when we travel for pilgrimages none of us carries a Christian and Muslim passport, we carry a passport of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. There is a need for the Nigerian government to embark

on a comprehensive nationwide economic empowerment programme, for democracy does not strive in poverty. Political zealots and religions chauvinists find ready tools in the teeming unemployed youths whose idle minds provide spacious workshop for the devil. There is a need for the Nigerian government to establish an independent religious equity commission with the role to prohibit all forms of religious discrimination, religious victimization, harassment, hate speeches and matters connected therewith.

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